

Full Research Paper

Assessing stakeholder dynamics in a restoration ecology Living Lab Using Social Network Analysis to Measure Collaboration and Participation

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Abstract

This study focuses on stakeholder collaboration within a living lab context. Living labs are often conceptualized as open innovation networks, where multiple stakeholders co-create, experiment, and learn together. This networked nature makes Social Network Analysis a particularly suitable array of methods to explore how collaboration evolves over time and analyse actors' role in driving (or limiting) collective action. We analysed the stakeholder network of a living lab focused on ecological restoration in a semiarid desertification-prone area in southeaster Alicante (Spain). A baseline network was mapped at the beginning of the initiative, and participation indicators were collected to examine the relationship between stakeholder position in the network and his/her degree of engagement. A second data collection will capture how the network evolved, allowing us to assess the living lab's impact on fostering collaboration. This approach will identify key actors, reveal collaboration dynamics, and inform strategic decisions to enhance stakeholder participation and restoration outcomes. By applying SNA in this context, we contribute to improve our understanding of living labs as evolving ecosystems of governance, innovation, and co-creation.

Key words

Living labs, open innovation networks, stakeholder collaboration, social network analysis, restoration ecology, participatory governance

Introduction

Many authors are pointing out the need for involving population in the development of ecosystem restoration projects (Fox and Cundill, 2018; Ostrom, 2009; Swart et al., 2018). In this sense, living labs are becoming popular as a tool for enhancing social participation. Among the diverse views and definitions of living labs, some authors consider them as open innovation networks (Leminen et al., 2012). Indeed, stakeholder collaboration is a key characteristic of Living Labs (Hossain et al., 2019), and from these interactions, we can expect a network to be created.

This setting provides an opportunity to analyse stakeholder interactions using social network analysis. With this approach, we can observe how relationships among stakeholders change over time due to their engagement in the living lab. It also allows us to explore if a stakeholder's position in the network (such as their level of centrality or connectivity) is related to their continued participation in living lab activities. For this purpose, we will use classical SNA metrics such as degree centrality (to measure overall connectivity), in-degree centrality (to identify actors with access to information/resources), and density (to assess overall network cohesion). To address this, the study is structured in two complementary levels of analysis: (i) the construction of stakeholder networks, and (ii) the measurement of participation indicators at the individual level. These two sets of data are then correlated to test whether network position is associated with participation (Figure 1).

Figure 1. A brief illustration of the data collection and data analysis.

To address this, we will build a network of the stakeholders of RENATUREM, a living lab in south Alicante which aims to fight against desertification. For this study, three different parameters will be measured: i) knowledge exchange among stakeholders, ii) professional collaboration and iii) resource exchange.

The knowledge exchange network will show communication flows among participants. Information exchange (Figure 2) will be represented by weighted links, with values depending on frequency of communication (daily, weekly, monthly, annually, or none). The collaboration network (Figure 3) will reflect how stakeholders work together and the number of projects they have worked on together. The resource exchange network (Figure 4) identifies resource sharing among stakeholders, indicating who was the provider and the type of resource involved (material or economic). These networks will be established at the beginning of the living lab and updated periodically to track changes over time using the open-access software Gephi.

Information exchange network

Figure 2. An information exchange network example.

Professional collaboration network

Figure 3. A professional collaboration network example.

Resources exchange network

Figure 4. A resources exchange network example.

Participation, understood as the involvement of stakeholders in decision-making processes (Reed et al., 2018), is a central goal of RENATUREM. To assess stakeholder participation in the living lab in southern Alicante, five main criteria will be used, combining the works of Arnstein (1969) and Eyssen et al. (2011) with RENATUREM’s specific goals to promote collaboration, resource sharing, and restoration activities:

- I. **Role of participation.** Based on Arnstein’s (1969) ladder of participation, seven roles are proposed, ranging from governance responsibilities to sharing information. These roles are: (1) responsibility in governance, (2) responsibility in a restoration project, (3) responsibility in living lab activities, (4) sharing resources with the community, (5) leading/participating in living lab activities, (6) attending activities, (7) sharing information. A stakeholder with more roles is considered to show a higher level of participation.
- II. **Attendance to activities.** The number of events a stakeholder attends, used as an indicator of engagement.
- III. **Communication.** Number of interactions via emails or WhatsApp with the living lab organization, including both responses and proactive messages.
- IV. **Proposals.** Number and type of proposals submitted by stakeholders (restoration projects, activities, improvements), identified through meeting minutes, email records, and dedicated submission channels.
- V. **Resource contribution.** Type and quantity of resources provided, including material, spatial, economic, volunteer work, or administrative support.

These indicators combine quantitative and qualitative data to capture different dimensions of participation.

To capture these dynamics, two networks will be constructed: one at the beginning of the living lab and another one year later. This will allow us to analyse how the overall structure of the network and the positions of individual stakeholders change over time. We will also examine how these changes relate to variations in participation metrics. By comparing stakeholder positions in the networks—such as their level of centrality or connectedness—with their participation indicators, we aim to explore whether a more central or active role in the network is associated with continued or increased engagement in the living lab. This will not only provide monitoring data, but also inform strategies to strengthen weak ties, support key actors, and enhance long-term sustainability of the living lab and the success of the restoration actions.

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